

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING PUBLIC WALKING TOURS IN SPORTS TOURISM

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Annotation: *This article shows that these methods are effective in developing a healthy lifestyle and strengthening the health of young people in the organization of mass hiking trips in sports tourism.*

Key words: *excursion, tourism, sport, classification, walking, events, tools, methods, forms, pedestrians, physical education.*

Health care should be understood not only as medical aid (medicines), but also various activities carried out through one or another means of physical education, especially hiking (tourism). Social living conditions, especially in labor processes. (getting to work, working and returning home) walking is done to some extent. These practical activities also have their own characteristics in terms of maintaining and improving health. But going to mountainous areas, river, lake, reservoir shores, green meadows, shady and cool places to have a rest and leisure, walking is a special thing. Because there are family members or a group (schoolchildren, students, workers, etc.), carrying the necessary equipment, clothes, food and carrying them, at least 10-15 km. Walking the distance (for a day) is considered the basis of travel. Every 30-45 minutes (it can change depending on the readiness of travelers) 3-5 minutes of short rest (priv-al), defecation ensures that the participants are not too tired. Observing the surroundings, studying the flora and fauna on the way increases the interest of travelers in natural scenery. The processes of going up and down, crossing hills, slopes, going down streams, jumping and crossing ditches and large bodies of water require strengthening of practical (physical) actions. Eating lunch, taking a rest (big priv-al), looking at the surroundings, bathing in clear waters strengthens health.

Walking tours of pupils and students are mainly organized for two purposes, i.e. to fulfill the requirements of "Health Tests" and to get acquainted with the environment. These trips can be one-day or overnight (2-3 days). Also, during the summer holidays (health camps and sports facilities), multi-day (8-10 or more) hiking trips are organized. Such trips are organized on the basis of annual plans of the council of physical culture teams of educational institutions (JMJ-sport club). In any educational institution, a tourism club or section (circle) is officially established, they also have independent plans.

Production enterprises in large cities of our country have their own characteristics due to their diversity. On this basis, in recent years, joint ventures have been established,

and the competence of production and the position of workers have greatly increased. Conditions are being created for them to engage in physical culture, sports, and tourism.

A number of sports circles (sections) or national teams are organized within sports clubs and unite many people. It is noteworthy that they include sections such as al-pinism, mountain tourism, auto tourism.

Another aspect is that under the leadership and patronage of trade union committees in enterprises, rest houses, health-sports centers are also operating in mountainous areas. It is important that their work includes travel. .

Rasul Hamzatov's philosophical lines, "Not an eagle that has not flown to the desert, not an eagle that has not returned from the desert to the mountain with prey" can be compared to travelers, that is, a person who has worked for years in a lonely corner and if he doesn't sleep in the beautiful scenery, sadness gathers in his heart. People who complain about their health or are sick do not know the value of clear waters, cool shadows, soothing breezes of the mountain. We want to say that intellectuals and some workers who have good opportunities and conditions are deprived of the bosom of nature.

There are countless stories, proverbs, and popular books about the health benefits of hiking. But there are many young and old workers, intellectuals, and various specialists who have not read them or are not interested in reading them. In addition, mass media, TV and radio broadcasts about travel and its essence in prolonging life, increasing work ability, and raising physical fitness are not carried out.

It is known that the participants of the hiking trip, especially those involved in tourism, need to be physically healthy, strong and trained.

For this reason, it is necessary to engage in special physical training in preparation for trips. For this, it is necessary to fulfill the following requirements: Pass a medical examination, get the consent and permission of doctors.

Performing physical education exercises (walking, jogging, 8-10 general development exercises) every day in the early morning. Depending on the comfort of the weather, wash in cold (warm) water up to half the waist and rub the body hard.

Active participation in physical education classes, sports training and competitions.

4-5 km in the evening (every day) if possible. to pass distances by brisk walking and running at moderate speed.

Measure blood vessels at rest before exercise (running). After the exercises (sometimes even in the interval), measure the pulse rate of the blood vessels and always compare them. See a doctor if there is a sudden change.

Measuring the level of physical development (pull-ups in the hands on the horizontal bar or trees, writing while leaning on the hands, lifting dumbbells or stones, sitting and standing with bent knees, etc.) and development and gradually increasing their amounts to go

Breathe in deeply (counting steps) and exhale slowly (counting steps) while taking slow, large steps. Controlling these cases and increasing the quantities.

There can be no doubt that these active activities have a positive effect on the physical fitness and development of pupils, students and workers.

It is recommended to play football, volleyball, basketball, tennis, badminton and take a bath in water bodies (river, canal) in the morning or evening free time, where there are conditions and opportunities.

Therefore, it is necessary to regularly engage in physical training and sports during the preparation process for hiking trips (in general, all the time). People who are used to it can overcome any difficulties encountered on trips or can endure them.

As described in the previous sections, hiking trips involve walking up and down hills, hills, mountains, and mountains with different movements. First of all, breathing deepens and panting occurs. Legs, waist, shoulders and arms are also tired. The strength of the legs and the strength of the back can be felt when jumping or jumping over a ravine, a ditch, a cliff, or a stone-barrier. In general, physical qualities such as dexterity, agility, and endurance are required. Those who are physically prepared before the trips or regularly engage in some kind of sports (especially athletics, gymnastics, swimming, basketball, etc.) will easily overcome the difficulties mentioned above.

Physical training during trips will be of great benefit in daily activities and labor (educational) processes in the future. For this reason, it is advisable to perform the following exercises in the process of traveling, that is:

1. During short (3-5 minutes) and long-term (5-10 minutes) stops (prival), to rest the legs, arms and back, walk slowly and move the arms to the side and up. swinging the elbows back and forth, twisting and turning the neck to the side. While lying down, raise your legs and lean on a rock, tree or bag (backpack). Take a deep breath of fresh air.

2. During lunch and breakfast, before eating, turn around (walk) to the sides, give light exercises for arms, legs, and body, after eating, with the permission of the leader, walk along a stream, a stream, or in a shady place. Playing football, volleyball, badminton (girls) depending on the time.

3. During overnight trips (1-2 days), exercise in the morning (running, hanging from trees, lifting stones, squatting, jumping around, etc.). Bathing in ice-cold water at noon, or bathing half-naked (partners must pour water). Lying in the sun naked to the waist, walking in the sun in light clothes, sitting and lying down in the shade. Take deep breaths (10-15 seconds) and deep breaths (10-20 seconds) while sitting and walking along with observing the environment when climbing high mountains and mountain rocks. Inhaling through the nose and exhaling through the mouth is close to the goal.

1.5-2 km depending on conditions before dinner. it is necessary to quickly cover the distance, jump and run in necessary places. Lifting stones (about 10-15 km) with two hands (10-20 times), pulling up trees with hands (8-12 times), lifting and lowering legs while lying on the back (girls) more repetitions of exercises are necessary.

In multi-day (10-15 or more) trips (in the conditions of health-sports facilities and recreation centers), there are many ways of physical training. In this case, a teacher or a

guide (methodist-instructor) conducts training regularly. Everyone should participate in it. However, some travelers (vacationers) can do their own physical exercise. In such cases, the following should be followed:

Carrying out usual morning physical exercises (walking, running, special: pull-ups, sitting, jumping, etc.) and increasing their quantity and standards.

Active participation in organized trips. Participating in classes (training) in the sport he loves Active participation in sports competitions.

Bathing in a basin (stream, canal, lake, etc.) 1-2 times a day (before noon and in the afternoon). Rapid ascent to high mountains, hills and peaks (together with the permission of the leader and 2-3 people). Walk half-naked in the sun, lie down (10-15 minutes), sit, lie down, and lie down in the shade and rest (do not sit or sleep for a long time) It should be noted that it is appropriate for students, students and workers to follow the above requirements and recommendations depending on the conditions when organizing multi-day (6-8) trips of their own accord. The conclusion is that the hiking trip is one of the important means of physical training of participants and participants as a socio-educational process. Yu.A. Shalokov, R. Abdumalikov, T. Kholdarov and others. according to the results of scientific research of specialists (see the list of references), the average life expectancy of people who regularly engage in tourism (hiking, mountain tourism, etc.) is 10-15 years longer than that of other people. Also, due to the high level of work ability, their productivity is 15-20% more than others. Among pupils and students, those who are engaged in tourism are much higher in mastering all subjects than others. Therefore, through travel, there are opportunities for physical training and growth of intelligence, increase of work skills, and most importantly, life extension.

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